

THE ROLE OF PHYTONYMS AND ZOONYMS IN THE FORMATION OF OIKONYMS (IN THE EXAMPLE OF JIZZAKH REGION)

Davurova Kholida Haydarovna

Senior teacher of the Department of Pedagogy and Languages of Tashkent Institute of
Humanitarian Sciences Doctor of Philosophy in Philology (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15284370>

***Annotatsiya.** Maqola oykonimlarning shakllanishiga bag'ishlangan. Ularning shakllanishida fitonim va zoonimlar alohida o'rin tutadi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** toponim, oykonim, fitonim, zoonim, fitooykonim, zoooykonim.*

***Аннотация.** Статья посвящается формированию ойконимов. В их формировании фитонимы и зоонимы занимают особое место.*

***Ключевые слова:** топоним, ойконим, фитоним, зооним, фитоойконим, зооойконим.*

***Annotation.** The article is dedicated to the formation of oikonyms. Phytonyms and zoonyms play a significant role in their development.*

***Keywords:** toponym, oikonym, phytonym, zoonym, phytooikonym, zoooikonym.*

The flora world of a specific region is reflected in its oikonyms, which are a type of toponym. Based on toponymic data, it is possible to determine what sorts of plants once grew abundantly in the researched studied area. For example, such practices can be observed in oikonyms like *Yonghoqlik* (Walnut Orchard), *Shuvoqzor* (Wormwood Field), *Olmazor* (Apple Orchard), *Tutli* (Mulberry Field), *Mingtut* (Thousand Mulberries), *To'ptol* (Dense Willow), and *Tikonli* (Thorny Place).

A group of toponyms have been developed based on the names of plants and trees. Settlements named after plants and trees are called phyto-toponyms. Phyto-toponyms (from the Greek “*phytos*” – plant) reflect the types of plants and the distinctive characteristics of the plant world in a particular region [3, p.8]. The emergence of such place names dates back to ancient times. Toponyms like *Oqterak*, *Olayoghoch*, and *Qorayoghoch*, mentioned in Mahmud Qashqari's “*Devonu lughati turk*”, are clear proofs of this idea [2, p.446].

Plants are closely connected with the material history of humankind and have played an important role in human life and economic activities. Naturally, they have served as a source of raw materials for people and they were abundant fodder for livestock. Therefore, people commenced using the names of various plants as place names. Such names served as specific reference points in the agricultural and pastoral lifestyles of tribes and peoples. Consequently, oikonym-type toponyms emerged.

Various phytooikonyms are quite common in the territory of Jizzakh region. In naming such places, words denoting the types of plants and trees play an active role. For example, the word “*jiyda*” (oleaster): *Chilonzor* is the name of a neighborhood in the Zomin district. The word “*Chilon*” is derived from the name of the *chilon jiyda* (a type of oleaster), and *Chilonzor* means “a village established in a place where chilon jiyda grows abundantly”.

Oikonyms formed with the word “*tut*” (mulberry): *Tutli* is a settlement in the Ghallaorol district. The mulberry tree, whose leaves serve as the main food source for silkworms, and its

fruit. *Tutli* means “a place where mulberry trees grow.” Another settlement in this district, *Yonboshtut*, also derives its name from the same word.

Oikonyms formed with the word “*tol*” (willow): *Qatortol* is a settlement in Bakhmal district. *Qatortol* means “a row of willows”. *Qoshtol* is a neighborhood in Zomin district. It refers to a place with two willow trees, distinguished by the presence of paired willow trees. *Tolli* is a village in Zomin district. *Tollisoy* is a settlement in Ghallaorol district. *Tollisoy* means “a stream where willows grow abundantly”.

Oikonyms formed with the word “*terak*” (poplar): *Toghterak* is a village in Zomin district, and this toponym means “a mountain with poplars”. The name *Mingterak* in Dostlik district also originates from the word “*terak*”, indicating a place associated with many poplar trees.

Oikonyms formed with the word “*chinor*” (sycamore or plane tree): *Mingchinor* is a village in Pakhtakor district. In the past, sycamore trees were planted in a desert area where *Heliotropium lasiocarpum* Fisch used to grow. As a result, the place came to be known as *Mingchinor*, meaning “a thousand sycamores”.

In phytooikonyms like *Qatortol*, *Mingterak*, and *Mingchinor*, words indicating quantity and number such as “*ming*” (thousand), “*to’p*” (cluster), “*qator*” (row), and “*gala*” (herd) are included in names to express the abundance of certain plants. These words indicate whether specific trees or plants are numerous or scarce in a given area. Street names like *Qatortut* in Jizzakh city and *Archaqator* in Bakhmal district have also been formed in a similar way.

Additionally, oikonyms formed with topoformants such as *-li*, *-zor*, and *-iston* grammatically indicate the abundance of specific types of plants in a given area. For example, oikonyms like *Betagali*, *Shilbili* (*Shilvili*) (Zomin district), *Uzumzor* (Pakhtakor district), and *Guliston* (G‘allaorol district) have been formed using such affixes. These suffixes help convey the idea that certain plant species are widely present in those locations.

Here are details about some of them: *Lolazor* is a village in Zafarobod district. *Lolazor* means “a place where tulips grow abundantly and bloom widely.” [6.P.33.]

Mevazor is the name of villages in Dostlik and Pakhtakor districts, which means *a place where many fruit trees grow* or *an orchard*.

Olmazor is the name of villages in Jizzakh and Bakhmal districts. In the past, these settlements were surrounded by large apple orchards that reflected in the name *Olmazor* [6.P.39.].

Besides, the names of villages such as *Pakhtazor* in Mirzachol district, *Chamanzor* in Pakhtakor district, *Jiydazor* in Zomin district, *Terakzor* in Dostlik district, *Niholzor* in Ghallaorol district, as well as street names like *Tokzor* in Arnasoy district and *Anorzor* in Dostlik district [1.B.41.] have all been formed by adding the topoformant *-zor* to a phytonym.

In addition, there are settlements named after various types of trees and plants across the region. These include fruit trees such as apple (*olma*), apricot (*orik*), hawthorn (*dolana*), and fig (*anjir*); non-fruit-bearing trees like sycamore (*chinor*), juniper (*archa*), jujube (*sada*), elm (*qayraghoch*), and poplar (*terak*); flowers; as well as wild and cultivated plants such as camelthorn (*yantog*), wormwood (*shivoq*), couch grass (*ajriq*), thorn (*tikon*), and reed (*qamish*). For example, *Olmalı* (Gallaorol district), *Orikli* (Zomin district), *Qamishli* (Forish district), and *Archali* (Zomin district) are oikonyms that belong to this category.

Based on the collected field materials, several oikonyms have been identified, including: *Qayraghochli*, *Olchali*, *Anjirli*, *Bedali* (Ghallaorol district), *Bodomzor* (Pakhtakor district),

Arpali (Bakhmal district),
Rayhonli, Pistali, Bodomli (Jizzakh city),
Yonghoqli (Forish district),
and *Gilosli* (Zafarobod district) [1.Б.42].

These place names reflect the presence and abundance of specific plants or trees in those areas.

Based on the collected field materials, toponyms such as *Qayraghochli, Olchali, Anjirli, Bedali* (Ghallaorol district), *Bodomzor* (Pakhtakor district), *Arpali* (Bakhmal district), *Rayhonli, Pistali, Bodomli* (Jizzakh city), *Yonghoqli* (Forish district), and *Gilosli* (Zafarobod district) have been identified [1, p.42].

In addition to plants, trees, and fruit trees, phyto-toponyms based on the names of flowers can also be found in the region. Examples of such toponyms include *Rayhon* (Sharof Rashidov district), *Boychechak, Nastarin* (Gallaorol district), and *Jasmin* (Bakhmal district) [1, p.42].

Phyto-toponyms that indicate the scarcity or limited number of plants often include appellative words such as “yakka” (single), “ikki” (two), “qo’sh” (pair), “uch” (three), “to’rt” or “chor” (four). Village names like *Qoshtol* (Zomin district), *Yakkatut, Qoshdarakht* (Bakhmal district), and *Qoshchinor* (Zafarobod district) are in this category. Other examples of phyto-toponyms formed with these words include neighborhoods such as *Yakkatol* (Forish district), *Yakkaterak, Uchterak, Torttol* (Jizzakh city), and *Yakkaqayraghoch* (Sharof Rashidov district) [1, p.42].

In addition, there are also phyto-toponyms used in their root form without any affixes. Examples include *Dolana, Tut, Archa, Chinor, Qayraghoch, Sada, Chilon, Qamish, and Arpa*. Such place names can be included *Dolana* in Bakhmal district, *Qamish* in Forish district, and *Chinor* in Ghallaorol district of Jizzakh region,

During the process of collecting information on the topic, Doctor of Philosophy in Philological Sciences Yu.O. Nematova also studied the phyto-toponyms in Namangan region by categorizing them according to plant and tree names. She provided examples such as:

- Plant names: *Qorayantoq* (Yangiqorqon district), *Qoratikan* (Uychi district), *Kanopli* (Pop district);
 - Non-fruit tree names: *Chinor* (Pop district), *Majnuntol, Buramatut* (Toraqorqon district), *Beshtol* (Chortoq district);
 - Fruit tree names: *Jiydazor* (Chust district), *Jiydakapa* and *Shaftoli* (Uychi district)
- [4, p.60].

In Jizzakh region, place names formed on the basis of zoonyms can also be found. The term “zootoponym” comes from the Greek words “zoo” – animal and “topos” – place [3, pp. 7–8]. Place names derived from the names of animals are called zootoponyms. These names provide valuable information about various animals that inhabit water reservoirs, forests, deserts, and steppe areas.

N. Okhunov studied zootoponyms by categorizing them into groups such as domestic animals, wild animals, aquatic animals, birds, and poultry in his work. Examples of such place names include *Otkhona, Eshakbuloq, Tulkiuya, Palangdara, Baliqkol, Qunduzbuloq, Kaptarkhona, and Zaghchakhona* [5, p.44].

Yu.O. Ne’matova, in her research, noted that the toponym *Kaklikqorqon*, located in the village of *Shorkent* in Chust district, is named due to the abundance of *kaklik* – partridge belonging to the pheasant family. She explained that the name *Kaklikqorqon* means “a settlement where partridges are abundant” [4, p.59].

Furthermore, in the toponymy of Jizzakh region, such place names can also be found. The origins of these names are based on the names of animals, birds, and other living creatures. For example, the village Laylakuya in Zomin district is a clear example of a zoo-toponym. As we know from nature, storks (*laylak*) typically inhabit areas near human settlements. Therefore, the place where storks would fly in and build nests came to be known as Laylakuya, meaning “*the place where storks dwell*” [7, pp. 93–94].

The village Jayrakhona in Forish district is also linked to the name of an animal porcupine. A porcupine belongs to the class of mammals, distinguished by its spine-like quills nestled in its fur, which serve a protective function. In the past, places inhabited by such animals were associated with Jayrakhona, meaning “*the place of jayras*”. Thus, a village located near an area where many porcupine lived came to be called Jayrakhona [7, p.119].

These kinds of place names, formed by the toponymization of animal and bird names, are known as zoo-toponyms. However, such zoo-toponyms are relatively rare in the Jizzakh region, which is considered one of the distinctive features of the area.

In conclusion, the phyto-toponyms of Jizzakh region stand out for their diversity and distinctive features. Many of the region’s place names have been formed based on the names of various plants. For instance, toponyms like Yakkatut, Qatortol, and Qoshtut reflect both the type and quantity of trees.

On the other hand, zoo-toponyms such as Laylakuya, Jayrakhona, and Borikhona are derived primarily from the names of animals and birds. These names hold a significant place in the toponymy of the region, contributing to its rich and unique linguistic and cultural landscape.

REFERENCES

1. Davurova Kh.H. Jizzak viloyati oykonimlarining lisoniy tadqiqi. Monografiya. – Toshkent: Best publish, 2024. – 140 b.
2. Mahmud Qoshg‘ariy. Devonu lug‘ati turk. – Toshkent, 1967. – 544 b.
3. Nizomov A., Rahimova G., Rasulova N. Toponimika. – Toshkent: Sharq, 2013. – 119 b.
4. Ne‘matova Yu. O. Namangan viloyati oykonimlarining tarixiy-lisoniy tadqiqi: Filol. fan. bo‘y. fals. dokt (PhD)... diss. – Farghona, 2018. – 161 b.
5. Okhunov N. O‘zbekiston toponimiyasi. – Qoqon, 2005. – 90 b.
6. Orinboev B. O‘. Jizzakh toponimlarining ta‘biri. – Samarqand, 2007. – 80 b.
7. Hakimov Q. M. Jizzakh viloyati toponimlari. – Jizzakh: Sangzor, 2014. – 203 b.